

Management Behavior of School Heads in Relation to School Performance

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Abstract:- The Philippine Department of Education's goals and objectives are supported and upheld by a range of leadership philosophies used by the Division of Masbate Province, which comprises the Placer East and West District. This study aims to identify the profile of school heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division in terms of sex, age, educational attainment, and length of service; management behavior of school heads; performance rating, and the management behavior of school heads in relation to school heads' performance in Placer District, Masbate Province Division.

The study used a Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire to collect quantitative data. It focused on the Management Behavior of School Heads in Relation to School Performance. The researcher selects explicitly all thirty-six (36) School Heads from Placer East & West District Public Elementary as respondents of the study. The study used percentage and chi-square (X^2) statistics as statistical tools in analyzing the data.

It shows that the most frequent value in the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire evaluation revealed that the frequent behavior of school heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division is the Passive-Avoidant Leadership. For school heads, performance 29 out of 36 or 80.6% of the school heads in Placer District Public Elementary got an OPCRF rating of 4.50-5.00 which is Outstanding in the OPCRF Adjectival Rating Scale while the remaining 7 out of 36 or the 19.4% only falls under Very Satisfactory in the OPCRF Adjectival Rating Scale.

It entails that the majority of Placer District school heads practice passive-avoidant leadership, which has little to no regard for the progress of followers and, if it persists, will result in the failure of progress initiatives, a reduction in the perception of the progress environment, and worse leadership outcomes.

The school heads' evaluated management behavior and school performance supports the hypothesis that management behavior has no significant relationship with the school performance and conclude that a significant relationship did not take place.

The Department of Education-Masbate Province Division in collaboration with Dr. Emilio B. Espinosa Sr. Memorial State College of Agriculture and Technology may provide a training/seminar/workshop for school heads. It may gather suggestions, inputs and experiences in the management behaviors of school leaders on how lead a progressive and quality oriented school.

Keywords:- Management, Behavior, School Performance, Transformational Leader, Transactional Leader, Passive-avoidant Leader.

I. INTRODUCTION

Leaders are individuals who direct, oversee, and support their team members, share their vision, drive change, and motivate and inspire the entire organization to perform better. The Division of Masbate Province, which includes the Placer East and West District, has a variety of leadership philosophies that support and uphold the aims and purposes of the Philippine Department of Education. This study targets to recognize the management behavior of Placer District school heads for there are several duties that fall under the purview of a school administrator, and quality management is one of them. There are school heads who has a behavior that holds the schools progress because of their lack of desire in adapting to new challenges being present in the community and in the department. How can a school leader ensure that children receive such high-quality education to come across the diverse desires of students in a certain community? In what manner can a school leader impose a lot of ideas that must be put into practice by the teachers. To be successful in an organization, today's academic leaders need a variety of leadership abilities (Thrash, 2009). Gmelch (2004) concurred that teaching leadership skills to academic leaders is necessary to reduce the lack of professionalism in administrative leadership. Academic leaders must choose their leadership style wisely in order to contribute significantly to the overall organizational success of their academic units (Del Favero, 2006).

Given the outline of leadership, its style and characteristics this study aspire to fathom the management behaviors and its relationship to school performance of school heads being transformational leaders of the Department of Education. Building principals are in charge of both instructional and administrative functions. Every community desires visionary leaders who can successfully

manage the day-to-day events that occur in every school. This isn't anything new. When should I exercise leadership and when should I manage the business? These are two of the most pressing and perplexing issues facing today's school administrators, particularly building principals.

Although there is a wealth of information about these two concepts in the literature, the message can be quite confusing. Management is primarily concerned with completing the organization's work in a capable and operative manner. Its primary emphasis is on getting the work done, with a typical focus on the organization's daily activities (Lalonde, 2010). Leadership, in contrast, concentrates on the future or what needs to be done. Vision, empowerment, and goal achievement are stressed (Lalonde, 2010).

Having a deep understanding about the Placer District school heads' management behavior gives the Department of Education SDO-Masbate Province a cause to organize and or create a suited seminar to enliven the passion, review the effectiveness of those school heads in performing well as school leaders. The ultimate goal of the study is to evaluate the management behavior of Placer District school heads, correlate its management behavior to school performance, and propose a suitable Management Style Refresher Seminar to Placer District school heads.

II. OBJECTIVES

This study investigates to achieve the following objectives: 1) What is the profile of school heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division in terms of sex, age, educational attainment, and length of service? 2) What are the Management Behavior of School Heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division? 3) What is the performance rating of School Heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division? 4) Is there a significant relationship in the Management Behavior of School Heads and the School Heads' Performance in Placer District, Masbate Province Division?

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study used a Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire to collect quantitative data. It focused on the Management Behavior of School Heads in Relation to School Performance. This was done between January to May 2023. The School Heads' of Placer East & West District Public Elementary were the participants of the research. There were (19) public elementary school in Placer East District and (17) public elementary school in Placer West District. A total of (36) public elementary school heads handling a school in Placer District. The researcher selects explicitly all the School Heads from Placer East & West District Public Elementary as respondents of the study.

The researcher followed a series of the protocol in the conduct of this study. Before officially conducting the study, a letter was sent to the office of the superintendent of Masbate Division in the Department of Education, In-charge

of both District, and to the school heads of public elementary schools in Placer East & West District. Upon approval, questionnaires were given directly to the School Heads of Placer East & West District as the study respondents.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are four main parts of the findings as depicted in this section: 1) Profile of school heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division in terms of sex, age, educational attainment, and length of service. 2) Management Behavior of School Heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division. 3) Performance rating of School Heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division. 4) Significant relationship in the Management Behavior of School Heads and the School Heads' Performance in Placer District, Masbate Province Division.

➤ *School Heads' Profile in Terms of Age*

Table 4a presents the profile of the school heads in Placer District Public Elementary in terms of age.

It indicates that the school heads of Placer District Public Elementary are as young as at the age of mid-30's but the most frequent age shown in the table are ages 46-50 which resulted to 27.8%.

Table 4a: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-25	0	0 %
26-30	0	0 %
31-35	1	2.8 %
36-40	2	5.6 %
41-45	9	25 %
46-50	10	27.8 %
51-55	7	19.4%
56-60	5	13.8%
60 above	2	5.6 %
Total	36	100 %

The primary goal of school leadership and or management is to raise the standard of instruction. Stress coming from age, school type, and school classification effects school heads' performance and happiness as they carry out numerous procedures to ensure the academic achievement and general growth of children, as well as the professional development of instructors. (Bedi et al., 2021; Darmody 2016; Elomaa et al., 2021).

It implies that age seem to have an effect on a leader's readiness to take the initiative, give orders, and give praise for achievement. This is because the longer they are at service as a school head the more opportunities are open for them to learn new set of leadership skills.

➤ *School Heads' Profile in Terms of Sexual Identity*

Table 4b presents the profile of the school heads in Placer District Public Elementary in terms of sexual identity.

It shows that most of the school heads' in Placer District Public Elementary are male which is at 69.4% paralleled to female which has only 30.6%.

Table 4b: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

SEX	Frequency	Percentage
Male	25	69.4 %
Female	11	30.6 %
Total	36	100 %

Despite the fact that they make up the majority, women have always been underrepresented in administrative positions of teaching positions in elementary and high schools. Women held only 30% of the major jobs in 2000. Only 13% of the superintendent positions are in public schools (Koch & Irby, 2002). Given how few women usually hold administrative positions, it is hardly unexpected that several academics in the 1970s, it was discovered that successful managers were predominately associated with stereotypically masculine characteristics (Vinnicombe, 1999).

It suggests that female school leaders in Placer Districts, Masbate Province Division are underrepresented in top-tier leadership positions for public elementary for some reasons that female leader prospects cannot continue their professional growth due to their responsibilities in their personal lives.

➤ *School Heads' Profile in Terms of Educational Attainment*

Table 4c presents the profile of the school heads in Placer District Public Elementary in terms of educational attainment.

Table 4c: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Doctorate Degree	3	8.3 %
With Doctoral Units	4	11.1 %
Master's Degree	9	25 %
With Master's Units	20	55.5 %
Total	36	100 %

It indicates that 55.5% of the school heads' in Placer District Public Elementary earned their Master's Units while the 25% are Master's Degree holder. Some of the school heads' earned their Doctorate Units which is only at 11.1%, however the remaining 8.3% of school heads' in Placer District Public Elementary finished their Doctors Degree.

With the majority of states now requiring a master's degree for school leadership roles, this historical perspective for educating educational leaders gives context for how educational requirements for service in K-12 educations have changed over time (Glass et al., 2000). Several states also necessitate more graduate-level education, professional growth, and in-service training to keep administrative licensing current (Glass et al., 2000).

It infers that the school heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division is fortified with graduate and post-graduate education level. There are only few who succeeded in their post-graduate education due to reasons that school heads are more focused in accomplishing the departments given activities and other relevant administrative duties, therefore time is more of a challenge for their graduate and post-graduate education journey.

➤ *School Heads' Profile in Terms of Length of Service*

Table 4d presents the profile of the school heads in Placer District Public Elementary in terms of length of service.

It shows that the length of service rendered by the school heads' in Placer District Public Elementary are at 25.0% who falls under 16-20 years in service which makes it logical for the reason that their age is also at their late-40's.

When school administrators are classified by age, number of years as an administrator, excellent success, and the kind of school being managed, the amount of leadership practices they employ is not noticeably different.

These findings imply that when respondents are categorized according to the profile characteristics, the level of leadership behaviors of school heads is comparable. (Aquino et al., 2021).

Table 4d: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 years	2	5.6 %
6-10 years	0	0 %
11-15 years	5	13.8 %
16-20 years	9	25 %
21-25 years	7	19.4 %
26-30 years	6	16.7 %
31-35 years	6	16.7 %
36-40 years	1	2.8 %
Above 40 years	0	0 %
TOTAL	36	100 %

It denotes that a school leader that is at service in public elementary for almost two decades is experienced enough on how to manage a public school environment. Experienced school heads had knowledge which they learned on the very field of the Department of Education which is very broad and can vary depending culture of what barangay the school is located, so school heads used their experience to successfully manage their school assignments.

➤ *School Heads' Management Behavior*

Table 5 presents the management behavior of the school heads in Placer District Public Elementary.

Table 5: Management Behavior of School Heads

Management Behavior	Mode	Rank
Transformational Leadership	3	3.5
Transactional Leadership	3	3.5
Passive-Avoidant Leadership	4	1
Outcomes of Leadership	3.50	2

TOTAL	36	
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It shows that the most frequent value in the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire evaluation revealed that the frequent behavior of school heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division is the Passive-Avoidant Leadership.

With the MLQ survey, the three leadership styles and nine subscales are developed and assessed using a Likert-type scale. The first leadership style on the MLQ is transformational leadership, which includes five subscales and depicts a leader that inspires subordinates to excel based on their initial level of confidence in achieving desired results. The subscales of transformational leadership focus on the principal's reported behaviors, influences, and capacity for motivating staff members. The five subscales are idealistic influence (attributed), idealized influence (behavior), inspiring motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration.

The second leadership style evaluated by the MLQ is known as transactional leadership, and it refers to leaders who operate within an organization's structure to identify followers' skills and give them jobs and responsibilities in order to get the necessary results. As a result of this leader negotiating with followers in an arrangement where rewards are exchanged for conformity, the desired results have been attained (Bass, 1985). The three transactional subscales assess how followers view a leader's exchange of ideas with them, how they react to corrections and criticism, and how they watch for rapid feedback or when expectations are not being met. Contingency compensation, management by exception (active), and management by exception (passive) are the three subscales.

Passive avoidant is the final type of leadership. The subscales of management by exception (passive) and laissez-faire represent a leader's decision to put off or postpone making decisions and delegate authority to others. This leader doesn't ask for much feedback and doesn't try to modify the situation much. Most experts agree that this literary approach is the least successful. Three outcome categories are also included in the MLQ: extra effort, effectiveness, and satisfaction (Avolio et al., 1999; Bass, 1990, 1998). There are three Extra questions, four Effectiveness questions, and two Satisfaction questions. Each of these variables represents how followers perceive the effects of the leadership decisions that were made. (B. Hardman, 2011).

It entails that mostly of Placer District School Heads manifest a management style of a passive-avoidant leadership where it shows little to no regard for the safety of followers, and if it persists, it will lead to unsuccessful safety initiatives, lowered perceptions of the safety climate, and poorer safety results. This management behavior can be get rid of if a suitable seminar is given fairly to all school heads in Placer District.

➤ *School Heads' School Performance*

Table 6 presents the school performance of the school heads in Placer District Public Elementary based from their OPCRf Rating.

Table 6: School Heads' Performance Rating

Performance	Frequency	Percentage
1.000-1.499 Poor (P)	0	0 %
1.500-2.499 Unsatisfactory (US)	0	0 %
2.500-3.499 Satisfactory (S)	0	0 %
3.500-4.499 Very Satisfactory (VS)	7	19.4 %
4.500-5.000 Outstanding (O)	29	80.6 %
TOTAL	36	100 %

It shows that 29 out of 36 or 80.6% of the school heads in Placer District Public Elementary got an OPCRf rating of 4.50-5.00 which is Outstanding in the OPCRf Adjectival Rating Scale while the remaining 7 out of 36 or the 19.4% only falls under Very Satisfactory in the OPCRf Adjectival Rating Scale.

As accountable for managing their schools' overall operations, it is essential that the school principals equip themselves with the knowledge and abilities that will serve as their weapon in managing their schools and ensuring that their students receive a decent education. The skills and credentials of school leaders, including their level of education, trainings taken, and years of position and prior experience as a school leader are variables that their capacity to lead at the school. Thus, these factors are constantly taken into account, especially when rating heads of schools. However, there are studies that suggest only the principals' individual attitudes cause them to be effective in his role as principal. (L. Perigrino et al., 2021).

It implies that the school heads in Placer District complies to the objective of the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form based on office and department goals, establishes performance standards and monitors employee progress.

➤ *Significant Relationship of School Heads' Management Behavior to School Performance*

Table 7 presents the significant relationship of school heads' management behavior to school performance of the school heads in Placer District Public Elementary.

Table 7: Chi-Square Tests for Management Behavior in relation to School Heads' Performance Rating

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	562.750 ^a	528	.143
Likelihood Ratio	175.515	528	1.000
N of Valid Cases	36		

Based from the chi-square test (X^2) result, the p-value is more than .05 ($p > .05$) which means that management behavior has no significant relationship with the school performance. Given their management abilities, school leaders' administration of their institutions directly affects how well those institutions operate in the educational sphere. Therefore, it is not unexpected that so many authors have offered their perspectives on these skills for school administrators (Mestry & Grobler, 2004; Monyatsi, 2005).

It indicates that the management behavior of school heads' does not affect the performance rating of the school.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings, the conclusions drawn are the following: 1) The school heads of Placer East and West District Public Elementary are in their mid-40's; most are male, many are with masters' units, and the majority have 16-20 years of experience as school heads. 2) The most frequent management behavior manifested by the school heads in Placer District, Masbate Province Division is the Passive-Avoidant Leadership which rated as Frequently, if not always in the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire scale. 3) The OPCRf rating of the School Heads' in Placer East and West District Public Elementary mostly have Outstanding Performance while some has Very Satisfactory Performance. 4) The school heads' evaluated management behavior and school performance supports the hypothesis that management behavior has no significant relationship with the school performance and conclude that a significant relationship did not take place.

The following are the recommendations formulated: 1) The school heads' in Placer District may pursue post-graduate studies. They could also undergo some training and attend seminars related to leadership and management to gain new strategies and techniques when leading and or managing a school. 2) Based on the management behavior of the school heads' in Placer District public elementary the area that needs utmost attention and action is the passive avoidant leadership which rated as Frequently, if not always in the MLQ scale; the Department of Education-Masbate Province Division may provide a training/seminar on how to lower passive-avoidant leadership presence in a school environment. 3) As for the school performance of the school heads, most of them got an OPCRf adjectival rating of outstanding but to obtain an overall outstanding adjectival rating the department heads should provide training/workshop to school heads to develop

and provide a top-tier school performance. 4) The Department of Education-Masbate Province Division in collaboration with Dr. Emilio B. Espinosa Sr. Memorial State College of Agriculture and Technology may provide a training/seminar/workshop for school heads. It may gather suggestions, inputs and experiences in the management behaviors of school leaders on how lead a progressive and quality oriented school.

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